

Assessment and Evaluation of Program Outcomes: Experiences of the School of Mechanical Engineering- Mapua Institute of Technology

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Abstract

The School of Mechanical Engineering of the Mapua Institute of Technology has recently undergone accreditation from one of the most respected accreditation organizations in the U.S., ABET, an accreditor for college and university programs in applied science, computing, engineering, and technology. The undertaking has provided the faculty and administrators from the Institute a unique set of experience and knowledge in outcomes-based education, unparalleled so far in the Philippines.

To keep abreast with the latest developments in the educational system worldwide, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has issued Memorandum Order (CMO) Number 09 Series of 2008- which requires all educational institutions in the Philippines offering a bachelor's degree in mechanical engineering to apply the outcomes-based approach in the development of their curriculum.

The minimum expected program outcomes (PO's) has been set by the CHED in its CMO, which eases the task of schools in formulating their own PO's. However, specific ways of assessing and evaluating of PO attainment has not been included in the CMO. This situation would most probably leave the institutions clueless as to how to formulate their own assessment and evaluation procedures to declare that they

have attained such prescribed outcomes. This paper, therefore, tries to address the problem by sharing some insights acquired by the School of Mechanical Engineering during the entire process of undergoing accreditation of its outcomes-based curriculum.

Introduction

Outcomes-Based Education (OBE) is one of the relatively new trends in education. OBE focuses on acquisition and mastery of certain knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, and other desired outcomes of education. OBE also involves the process of assessment and evaluation of outcomes attainment and continuous improvement of the educational program (Butler 2004). The highlight of OBE is its switch in emphasis from traditional input-based methodologies to outcomes-focused education.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has acknowledged the importance of keeping pace with current global trends in education. For this reason, it has initiated CHED Memorandum Order No. 09 series 2008 (CMO), which aims to rationalize the undergraduate mechanical engineering program offered in the Philippines. One of the identified means of rationalization is for Institutions offering a BS-Mechanical Engineering program to ensure that students acquire the minimum set Program Outcomes (POs) upon graduation (CHED 2008).

However, the CMO was limited in providing information on the conduct of the assessment and evaluation of the POs that it required to be incorporated into the programs.

POs are general statements that depict what students are expected to know and be able to do by the time of graduation- skills, knowledge, and behaviors are some expectations from students throughout their stay in the program (ABET 2008). Course Outcomes (COs), which are related to the POs, are specific outcomes that are expected to be acquired or exhibited by students upon completing a course.

The School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering of the Mapua Institute of Technology has recently been accredited by ABET, which is one of the most respected accreditation organizations in the United States for college and university programs in applied science, computing, engineering, and technology. The administrators and faculty members of the Institute have gained a significant level of experience and knowledge in OBE from the accreditation visit- especially in the aspects of assessment and evaluation. The School would like to share the knowledge and experiences gained from the accreditation process to help other colleges and universities in their development of their own world-class outcomes-based mechanical engineering curriculum.

Assessment

Assessment pertains to the process of obtaining data, quantitative or qualitative, which can be used for the purpose of measuring achievement (Rogers 2002). In OBE, various parameters are assessed to determine the extent to which the Program

Educational Objectives (PEOs) and the POs have been attained. Discussion about assessment of PEOs will not be covered in this paper due to its wide scope and will be tackled in a separate future publication.

The CMO identifies POs that are expected to be attained by the students of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering the mechanical engineering program. Such POs, labeled from A to I, are shown in table 1.

Table 1. POs identified by CMO 09 s.2008

a.	An ability to apply knowledge of mathematics, science and engineering.
b.	An ability to design and conduct experiments, as well as to analyze and interpret data.
c.	An ability to design a system, component or process to meet desired needs within realistic constraints.
d.	An ability to function on multi-disciplinary teams.
e.	An ability to identify, formulate and solve engineering problems.
f.	An understanding of professional and ethical responsibility.
g.	An ability to communicate effectively in both Filipino and English languages.
h.	An understanding of the impact of engineering solutions in a global and societal context.
i.	An ability to use techniques, skills and modern engineering tools necessary for mechanical engineering practice .

The POs shown above are the minimum requirements set by the CMO, and may be further expanded by the respective HEIs. In the case of the School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering of Mapua Institute of Technology, the Institute has adopted additional POs in accordance with the minimum requirements of ABET (POs set by ABET are shown in table 2). After setting the minimum POs, the next step taken by the School was to assign various courses offered that were deemed to be highly relevant to the POs. An example of such PO-to-course matching is provided in table 3.

Table 2. POs identified by ABET

a.	An ability to apply knowledge of mathematics, science, and engineering
b.	An ability to design and conduct experiments, as well as to analyze and interpret data
c.	An ability to design a system, component, or process to meet desired needs
d.	An ability to function on multi-disciplinary teams
e.	An ability to identify, formulate, and solve engineering problems
f.	An understanding of professional and ethical responsibility
g.	An ability to communicate effectively
h.	The broad education necessary to understand the impact of engineering solutions in a global and societal context.
i.	A recognition of the need for, and an ability to engage in life-long learning
j.	A knowledge of contemporary issues
k.	An ability to use the techniques, skills, and modern engineering tools necessary for engineering practice.

Table 3. Example of PO-to-course matching.

KEY COURSES	PROGRAM OUTCOMES										
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k
UNDERGRADUATE THESIS - 3				✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		
RENEWABLE ENERGY								✓		✓	
PLANT VISIT AND INSPECTION									✓		
CONTROLS ENGINEERING											✓

Upon identification of courses that were relevant to the various POs, the School set Course Outcomes (COs) that are relevant to the PO or POs identified for a particular course. An example of such COs and their relationship with respective POs are shown in table 4 below. Table 4 shows some COs for the course thermodynamics and their relationship with the POs.

Table 4. Relationship between COs and POs

Course Outcomes	Program Outcomes										
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k
Understand the fundamental concepts and laws governing mechanical engineering thermodynamics.	✓										
Understand, analyze and solve problems involving thermodynamics processes.	✓										
Calculate the heat, work, net work, efficiency and other parameters for given thermodynamic cycles.	✓										

After setting the relationship between identified COs and POs, the School then chose the best assessment tools to be used to measure the degree of attainment of the COs and the POs.

Assessment tools vary depending on many factors. The School took consideration of many suggestions from Rogers that assessment tools should be based on an assessment plan developed by both faculty and administrators. The assessment plan should primarily take into consideration the following: its effectiveness and appropriateness to assess COs and POs, manageability of the assessment process, assessment strategy alignment with PEOs and the input of various constituents (students, alumni and industry) and flexibility of the plan (Rogers 2004).

Both traditional and newly created assessment tools were utilized by the School. Such tools included quiz questions (take note total quiz or examination scores were not used), oral presentations, case studies, design projects and performance appraisals, to name some. All assessment scores were then converted using a rubric,

which easily defines the level of attainment of assessed parameters. An example of the rubric developed and used by the School is shown in table 5. Scores derived for measuring CO attainment were then averaged to get the PO attainment of a particular course. All PO scores were then collated for evaluation purposes. Proof of sources of assessment scores were kept as portfolio exhibit for future reference.

Table 5. Example of rubric used for assessment of COs.

Score	Equivalence	Description
1	Very poor	The student was not able to demonstrate the expected outcome
2	Poor	The student was able to demonstrate the expected outcome, but level of demonstration was less than the acceptable level
3	Fair	The student was able to demonstrate the expected outcome satisfactorily
4	Good	The student was able to demonstrate the expected outcome in an advanced manner
5	Excellent	The student was excellent in demonstrating the expected outcome

An important note to educators who would like to adapt or are currently utilizing OBE is that finals grades or total quiz scores should not be used as an assessment tool since such measurements do not reflect the attainment of a specific CO. Final grades and total scores are usually an aggregate of scores, some of which are not related to the CO or PO of interest. Use of total scores as assessment tools would result in data that does not reflect reality.

Evaluation

Rogers (2002) defined evaluation as the process of analyzing data gathered from assessment for the purpose of knowing the value of the data obtained and providing

information for future actions to be taken. Scores from the assessment process are collated to form a collection of useful information, which will be used for effective evaluation of PO attainment and future improvements in the program.

Majority of faculty members in the School are engaged in the evaluation process. Scores from COs are evaluated in Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), which are done at least twice a year. The FGD is conducted among faculty members from “course clusters” (courses categorized and clustered according to their relevance e.g. thermofluids and machine design). The FGD also computes the PO attainment scores from the collection of the CO scores and may determine right away if there are courses or CO that are in need of immediate addressing or prioritizing. The results of the evaluations from the FGDs are then discussed in the Program Committee Meeting (PCM), which is held at the end of every assessment cycle (once a year). The PCM is attended by faculty members assigned as “cluster heads” and the dean.

Aggregate scores and faculty inputs from the FGDs are taken into consideration in the PCM. The outputs from the PCM are composed of quantified scores, which measure the attainment level of each of the POs, and the qualitative inputs from the faculty members. The program committee then arrives at strategies on how to better improve the PO attainment scores, and eventually the program itself. Strategies to better improve the program are set to be implemented in the next assessment cycle, thus completing the Continuous Quality Improvement process of the Institute.

Final remarks

OBE is a necessity in the current global landscape of engineering education. HEIs must convert from input-based instruction to OBE, not only to be in accordance with the CMO, but also to be globally competitive and relevant. For a HEI to effectively implement OBE, the general aspects must be revisited, understood and identified. Such aspects include the mission, vision, and PEOs. An HEI must also consistently ensure that the mission and vision are met. One of the means to ensure that such are satisfied is through attaining the PEOs and POs. Assessment and evaluation are thus very important processes in ensuring that students are able to acquire and demonstrate the outcomes that HEIs deem to be necessary for their students to become productive members of society and much better engineers.

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